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Simulating the energy yield of bifacial photovoltaic modules installed on carports or canopies

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ABSTRACT: The installation of solar photovoltaic (PV) modules on carports or canopies is a relatively popular application of PV power generation. This advantageously combines power generation and shaded parking for vehicles in the case of carports, or power generation and shelter and shade for people, animals or goods with little waste of land. In parallel, bifacial technology has experienced a swift increase in its share of the PV market in recent years, which opens the door to various improvements and even new kinds of solutions. However, in current state-of-the-art PV simulation tools, the added complexity introduced by bifacial technology and by the complex geometry of PV installations on carports or canopies is still not fully covered and the evaluation of the bifacial energy gain (BEG) is not always accurate. In this work, a novel simulation tool is introduced, which benefits from the latest 3D evaluation libraries incorporated into the Graphic Processor Unit (GPU) of modern computers, as developed for the video game industry. This novel approach provides an evaluation of the BEG with a spatial resolution that is similar to what is achievable with backward ray-tracing techniques but within a tiny fraction of the required simulation time. With this, it is possible to simulate the energy yield of the PV plant accurately and in detail, such as for commercial projects.

Keywords: Bifacial, PV, simulation, BEG, GPU, carport, canopy, photovoltaic plants

1 INTRODUCTION

The installation of solar photovoltaic (PV) modules on carports or canopies is a relatively popular application of PV power generation. This advantageously combines power generation and shaded parking for vehicles in the case of carports, or power generation and shelter and shade for people, animals or goods with little waste of land in the case of canopies [1]. In parallel, bifacial technology has experienced a swift increase in its share of the PV market in recent years, which opens the door to various improvements and even new kinds of solutions [2]. However, in current state-of-the-art PV simulation tools, the added complexity introduced by bifacial technology is still not fully covered and the evaluation of the bifacial energy gain (BEG) is not always accurate. Some considerations are particularly important for PV installations with bifacial modules on carports or canopies, as follows:

- Arrays cannot be assimilated to “infinite” rows, as is usually done in commercial software solutions based on 2D view factors for bifacial computation [3]. Consequently, it is important to properly consider the 3D border effects on the BEG.

- Structures can be installed using different set ups or layouts depending on the location and the possible combined use of the land, hence customized distributions of dispersed elements need to be considered. This means that specific interference effects between the structures due to ground shading need to be evaluated with a case-by-case approach. This increases the number of analyses that are required, which can be very demanding in terms of computation resources.

- Ground albedo can vary for various reasons over time, so that seasonal, directional, and spectral effects need to be considered. This requires a more sophisticated approach than the simplistic Lambertian reflectance assumption for any surface that is used in conventional tools; instead, the reflectance of each material needs to be

modelled with the help of a bidirectional reflectance distribution function (BRDF) that is specific to each reflecting surface. [4]

This study presents the lessons learned from the evaluation of the energy yield of several PV projects using bifacial modules on carports and canopies located in France. A novel simulation tool, using advanced computing techniques, is introduced here. This novel approach provides an evaluation of BEG with a spatial resolution that is similar to what is achievable with backward ray-tracing techniques [5], but within a tiny fraction of the required simulation time. With this, it is possible to simulate the energy yield of such small PV plants accurately and in detail, which is necessary for commercial projects.

2 METHODOLOGY

The evaluation of the bifacial energy gain is carried out with a novel simulation tool based on the use of the latest 3D evaluation libraries incorporated into the Graphic Processor Units (GPU) of modern computers. These libraries were developed for the video game industry, but they now appear useful in a variety of other demanding applications where realistic and accurate visualization is important. The achievable spatial resolution is similar to what is possible with backward ray-tracing techniques, but only necessitates a tiny fraction of the latter’s required simulation time. The method behind the use of GPUs for solar energy application has been described elsewhere, e.g., for the evaluation of complex shading problems [6] and for the evaluation of bifacial irradiance [7]. Overall, the novel approach proposed here provides a detailed and accurate simulation of the energy yield of various types of PV installations, including for the small commercial projects investigated here.

3 APPLICATIONS

3.1 Carports

The evaluation of the bifacial energy gain in applications such as PV carports requires an accurate modelling of the 3D geometry on the PV array and its surrounding environment, as well as a good modelling of the reflectance of the associated materials. The approach used here benefits from the power of GPUs in modern computers, as mentioned above. The principle is simple: From each side of each PV panel, a 180° spherical view over different points of the module is created, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Spherical view as seen from one point of the PV array located on the backside of one PV module.

A tradeoff must be considered between computation time and accuracy. An optimum can be found, depending on the number of viewpoints and their location over the PV plant. As a reference, the pictures are generated here at a resolution of 512 x 512 pixels, which is equivalent to more than 250,000 rays if rather using a ray-tracing technique. These pictures (or alternative rays) are nevertheless obtained relatively fast (≈ 10 – 20 ms per picture).

There are several possible contributors to the source of incident irradiance. Some PV elements are lit by direct sunlight or by skylight, whereas others are shaded from the sun but can still receive some part of the reflected diffuse radiation that comes from the surrounding ground or objects. In the present approach, each component needs to be evaluated separately, and a correct incident irradiance magnitude must be calculated for the radiation emanating from the sun, sky, and various surface elements.

A virtual mesh is spread over the surface of all the ground-reflecting elements and any object that would be relevant, because in the immediate environment of the PV modules. For the case of carports, the ground is the flat parking lot covering (e.g., asphalt), and the relevant objects are typically the parked cars, and to a lesser extent the support structures. The mesh constitutes an ensemble of points from where the visibility to the sky is

evaluated. Another important optimization must be made on the spatial resolution of this mesh to obtain accurate results without inducing exaggerated computation times. Figure 2 shows a typical mesh used on the ground and cars for the evaluation of sky-view factors.

Figure 2: Mesh on ground and car for the evaluation of sky-view factors.

Once the mesh has been defined, the evaluation of the sky-view factors between each point of this mesh and the sky is carried out, which provides a sun + sky visibility potential. This is a purely geometric parameter, which takes any value between 0 (sky fully blocked) and 1 (sky fully visible). Figure 3 shows an example of the sky view as seen from one particular point of the mesh located on the ground, as visualized in a spherical view.

Figure 3: Sky view as seen from one particular point of the mesh on the ground, visualized in a spherical view.

The result of the calculation of the sky-view factors for each point of the mesh on the ground, cars and other key objects provides a 3D map of these view factors over the whole simulation scene. Figure 4 shows the spatial variation of the sky-view factors from the ground, obtained by visualization as a heatmap. Similarly, Figure 5 shows a closer view on such a heatmap for the sky-view factor originating from the front side of a car.

Figure 4: Heatmap showing the spatial variation of the sky-view factor as seen from the ground and cars.

Figure 5: Heatmap showing the spatial variation of the sky-view factor as seen from the ground and the cars.

In parallel, Figure 6 shows the spatial variation of the sky-view factors to the ground and cars as seen from one specific point located on the backside (facing down) of a PV module installed on the carport. The spatial distribution of these sky-view factors directly conditions the reflected irradiance incident on the selected element of the PV array.

Figure 6: Spatial map of the sky-view factors to the ground and cars as seen from one specific point located on the backside of a PV module installed on a carport.

The reflectance of any material that reflects sunlight or skylight in the environment of a carport is usually complex to model. This is because (i) spatial variability

in reflectance properties can be significant from one object to the other; (ii) on-site measurements are often not available for reasons of budget, personnel, or time constraints; and (iii) the reflectance of these elements can be relatively asymmetric, time varying, and sometimes spectrally variable. The exact procedures to evaluate the reflectance patterns using the BRDF approach is out of the scope of this report, but is described in other studies [2].

To implement the effect of albedo, we apply a different method for the diffuse component and for the direct component of the irradiance.

For the diffuse component, the sky-view factors obtained in Figure 6 need to be weighted by the albedo of each element seen in the spheric view (for this example, 0.1 for the ground and 0.3 for the cars). The result of the application of such a weighting procedure is illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Field of view weighted by the albedo of the different objects seen from a point on the backside of a PV module.

The integration of all the pixels in Figure 7 provides a value (0.047 as shown in Figure 8b) that multiplied by DFI_{iso} provides the irradiance from the sky that is reflected to the node of the mesh where the spheric view is created.

For the contribution of the reflected direct irradiance from the sun, we create the view seen in Figure 8a, taking into account the sun position with respect to each object, and the shading from other elements for the directional properties of the reflectance. As done before, the integration over all the pixels of Figure 8a provides a value (0.062) that once multiplied by the direct irradiance indicates the contribution of that component to the irradiance reflected onto the node of the mesh where the spheric view is created.

On the front face, the direct and diffuse components of the irradiance are computed through other weighting factors shown in Figure 8c and 8d and that indicate the level of shading applied to the direct solar irradiance from the solar disk and to the isotropic diffuse irradiance from the rest of the sky.

Figure 8: Views from a specific solar cell of the carport canopy: a) elements under direct sunlight; b) diffuse irradiance view-factor reflection from the sky; c) shading factor for parallel rays on the front side of the same cell; and d) sky elements direct view from the front side.

Repeating the process for all each element of the complete PV plant makes it possible to generate a heatmap of the irradiance distribution over both the front and rear module surfaces, as shown in Figure 9. That heatmap is a critical step towards analyzing inhomogeneities in the irradiance field and evaluating their mismatch-induced electrical impact through different possible methodologies.

Figure 9: Irradiance distribution over the complete PV array

Once the incident irradiance profile has been obtained for each PV cell composing the PV plant, and for each 10-min time interval of the year, the irradiance is converted into PV power using a PV simulation model

that accounts for all PV conversion losses in the whole system. For most of these energy losses, standard simulation routines can be used, because several of them are available and widely known [3], [8], [9], [10], [11]. The differences between these alternative models are beyond the scope of this study and are not relevant to its central topic.

Among the energy losses that need particular attention, the additional mismatch losses that are caused by the spatially inhomogeneous irradiance distribution on the PV modules need to be cautiously addressed. Several possibilities exist to simulate the impact of uneven irradiance distributions on the electrical mismatch losses. The most accurate method is to generate I-V curves for the whole PV system, considering the mapping of the irradiance down to cell level. This, however, is a very demanding exercise in terms of computing power. Other alternatives have been developed in the literature. One of them is selected here: it consists of a parametric model that estimates the mismatch losses as a function of the overall degree of inhomogeneity of the irradiance incident on the PV array [12]. This model has produced annual losses values in the range of 0.3% to 1%, depending on the specificities of each PV project.

Once the PV power is obtained for each time interval, the energy yield is calculated after summation over the time period considered.

3.2 Canopies

Similar to the installation of PV modules on carports, several others PV array configurations on canopies can benefit from bifacial energy gain. Bifacial PV modules mounted on canopies are increasingly encountered in the rural environment, in particular in agrivoltaic contexts, where the canopies are used as shelters for farm animals, some types of crops, agriculture machinery, or other farm buildings.

The geometry of these canopy installations is normally less complex than in the case of carports. For instance, Figure 10 illustrates a PV installation on canopies over a grassy field.

Figure 10: PV installation on canopies over a grassy field.

One major difficulty for the evaluation of the bifacial energy gain (BEG) in rural environments is the accurate assessment of the reflected radiation, in particular when emanating from vegetation. Predicting the reflectance properties of any object at any moment is particularly complex. Among other reasons, this complexity is caused by: (i) the lack of databases providing reliable field measurements of reflectance under well-defined conditions, (ii) the anisotropic nature of reflectance patterns, (iii) the spatial diversity and spectral sensitivity of reflectance, and (iv) its temporal variability (both

diurnal and seasonal). It appears that the sensitivity of reflectance to some of these factors is generally higher in the case of natural materials such as vegetation, soil, stones, etc. than in the case of the artificial materials encountered in urban environments, such as asphalt or concrete. The exact assessment of this kind of reflectance is out of the scope of this work.

Even with a simplified geometry, significant inhomogeneities can appear in the spatial distribution of the reflected solar irradiance on the backside of PV modules, such as illustrated in Figure 13. Typically, the reflected irradiance is lower in the middle of the PV array, higher over the edges, and even higher at the corners. This is a direct consequence of the higher view factors for the points on the module backsides that are located closer to the edges and corners. When the points under scrutiny are situated closer to the center of the PV array, the surrounding PV modules contribute to decreasing the effective field of view. On the other hand, those PV modules that are situated in the center of the PV array also receive less reflected irradiance because a more important fraction of the underlying ground tends to be shaded. This inhomogeneity, if significant, can lead to additional electrical mismatch losses, as already discussed in the case of PV carports.

Figure 13: Distribution of the incident irradiance on the backside of bifacial PV arrays, showing an inhomogeneous spatial distribution.

4 CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

The number of installations with bifacial PV modules on carports or canopies is fast increasing. The bifaciality of the PV modules offers interesting advantages in this kind of configuration.

The accurate simulation of the energy gain for these PV installations is however challenging. This is still a rather new kind of application, and many challenges still lie ahead towards a more accurate assessment of the energy yield of these PV plants.

Among the most challenging topics are the need for accurate albedo values and reflectance profiles, including angular and spectral considerations. Another challenge is the accurate modelling of the 3D scenes that can be very complex, and the relatively high sensitivity of the bifacial energy gain to the geometric of the environment.

The GPU-based method presented here has already been used to assess the bifacial energy gain of many large bifacial PV plants totaling more than 1 GW since 2017, with a large diversity of applications, including large PV plants with fixed structures or trackers, carports, canopies in rural areas, greenhouses, or vertical agrivoltaic structures. Several application cases have been illustrated

in this article. The further development and scientific validation of this method is currently ongoing in the context of two European R&D projects: the H2020 project SERENDI-PV, and the COST project Pearl-PV. However, given the increasing diversity of bifacial PV installations, and the scarcity of reliable monitored operation data that are currently available, more effort and more collaboration will be needed in the future in order to incorporate and validate new functionalities in the tool. In this context, collaboration proposals are welcome, on the research effort as well as on the analysis of the operation data of bifacial PV installations.

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